

ASPECTUAL PHASES EXPRESSED BY SEMANTIC UNITS

Saloxiddinov M.Sh.¹

Abstract:

This article analyzes the aspectual phases expressed in English and Uzbek languages, highlighting that each semantic component has its own unique combination, and that the subject's activity or movement that is not directed towards any object has several distinctive variants. Furthermore, it focuses on the first of these semantic structures, which is considered the subject and its specific movement, emphasizing its expression of concepts such as beginning, duration, completion, multiplicity, and iterativity (repetitiveness).

Key words: resultativity, iterativity, multiplicativity, processuality, phase.

It is known that beginning, duration, and completion are traditionally expressed through the concept of aspectuality in grammar. However, the concepts of beginning, duration, and completion differ from these notions in their nature. These concepts do not denote situations but rather their modifiers. They are also considered to have semantic features. Semantic features consist of deictic tools that indicate the relationship between a word and a text. These concepts can be divided into two categories. The first category includes those that are structurally simpler. Specifically, the concepts of resultativity, iterativity, and multiplicativity belong to this group. The second group includes concepts that are structurally more complex. This group includes concepts such as initiation, processuality, duration, and completion. Processuality typically arises through the influence of temporal indicators and the actional semantics of verbs. These temporal determinants are expressed through adverbs and phrases that indicate the occurrence of an action over a certain period, such as "for a long time," "during," "for a while," and so on.

The concepts of beginning, duration, and completion can also be divided into two categories. The first category includes aspectual meanings that fall under the traditional term of aspect, which are typically expressed in English through aspectual verbs (to begin, to start, to go on, to stop, etc.) and the combination of impersonal verb forms. The second category encompasses all linguistic means that convey these meanings. The concept expressing the meaning of beginning may seem simpler from a semantic construction perspective, but it appears more complex when viewed structurally. From a structural perspective, this concept is studied within the framework of words, simple sentences, and texts.

Let's pay attention to the following examples: "That's what that day began with" (Barth: 74). In this example, the verb "to begin" indicates the start of an event or situation. From a structural point of view, a proposition is formed, and the word "day" serves as a modifier. Similarly, the phase expressed by such a verb can also occur within the entire simple sentence. For example: "The lobby became a clearing station, with hasty aid for those still living" (Austen, 59). In general, meaning or content may remain undefined within a single sentence. For instance: "This started some words upon grocery men and the cost of food in general" (Th. Dreiser, 52). In such cases, only small episodes expressed by the phase verb can reveal the entire meaning and content of the beginning. For example: "The price of pictures, moreover, had if anything gone up, and he had done better with his collection since the war began than ever before" (J. Galsworthy, "The Forsyte Saga (III)"); "I began my speech with the words of greeting" (Maugham: 231). Additionally, deictic pronouns can indicate the focal point of the beginning phase concept: "He is the sort of man that ends up a millionaire" (Heller, 76).

The concept of duration also stands out with various semantic properties when analyzed from a structural perspective. Let's focus on the following example: "He kept standing, leaning on the wire, as though he had all day before him, and kept on smiling" (Show, 512).

The concept of completion is semantically divided into two types: completion and result. The structural composition of these phenomena also arises in the expression of complex and

¹ Saloxiddinov Manuchexr Sharofiddinovich, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Teacher

simple situations. For example: "With the commencement of the rain, the lightning gradually ceased" (Cronin, 56); "Throughout the interview, she kept her temper perfectly, laughing and jesting in a slightly patronizing way at her husband, whereas Mor by the end of it was reduced to almost speechless anger" (Murdoch: 104); "All the walk was delightful, and though it ended too soon, its conclusion was delightful too" (Austen, 403). In the first example, the aspectual verb indicates the completion of a situation, while in the second example, the aspectual verb expresses the result.

Each semantic composition that expresses aspectual phases has its own specific combination. For instance, when we consider the subject and its activity or movement directed towards an object, several distinctive variants can be observed. The first of these semantic structures involves the subject and its specific action, expressing the following concepts: beginning, duration, completion, multiplicity, and iterativity (repetitiveness). The second structure relates to the "subject's thinking and speech activity," which can also generate the aforementioned concepts.

Furthermore, duration can be expressed through core and peripheral means. Core means include the aspect-tense forms of verbs in English, along with the characteristics of boundedness/unboundedness of verbs. Auxiliary means can include linguistic tools that do not have formal distinctions and are used within the text. Core means arise at the paradigmatic level of duration, manifesting with both bounded and unbounded verbs. Auxiliary means emerge at the syntagmatic level, where prepositions, postpositions, and other nominative characteristics in context are utilized.

In English, continuity primarily arises within the framework of tense forms (continuous form). In these cases, continuity emerges regardless of the aspectual properties of the verbs. The continuity expressed in the indefinite form primarily occurs based on the boundedness/unboundedness characteristics of the verbs and within the context. This tense form of the verb indicates an indefinite continuity or processuality that aligns with the aspectual properties of the verb. In this case, they signify the ongoing nature of the action expressed by the predicate through aspectual contextual means. Here, continuity is expressed under the influence of the verb's aspectual properties and other non-verbal markers. The duration of the action is viewed as a flow in time. For example: "I move from town to town" (Bulgakov). "Whenever he sees her, she is always reading" (Mitchell).

In addition to the three major concepts mentioned, there are also other minor semantic notions interpreted within the scope of aspectuality. It is known that actions, situations, and events are reflected in the sequence and enumeration from the perspective of language in human consciousness.

The views expressed by Western linguists regarding aspectual phases are also relevant. V. Croft divides phase analysis into two types: the analysis of temporally bounded phases of events and the analysis of unbounded types of phases. Timberlake proposes four types of phases. He considers quantitative changes in a state as part of the phase phenomenon. [Timberlake; 35-57, 46]. V. Croft argues that distinguishing only three phases disregards certain phenomena and that the adaptation of phases expresses the aspectual contour of events. According to him, temporal characteristics play a crucial role in phase analysis [Croft William: 54].

Parsons, on the other hand, directs phase analysis towards Z. Vendler's aspectual classification. He enumerates three types of phases: development phase, culmination or completion phase, and holding phase [Parsons T, 1990: 4-23]. The author emphasizes that predicates indicating the type of state constitute the "holding" phase. He considers the aspectual types of accomplishments and achievements to belong to the culmination or completion phase. Specifically, in the example "Henry won the race," winning the competition pertains to the culmination phase, while the continuous tense form of the verb in this example signifies the "development" phase.

The scope of expressing aspectual phases can limit the diversity of aspectual meanings that arise within specific combinations. Therefore, phase research should not focus solely on the composition of specific combinations within the predicate domain, but it is important to consider all grammatical and lexical means.

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